

Comparative Effect of Simulation and Cooperate Learning Methods of Instruction on NCE Students' Academic Achievement in Automobile Technology in Colleges of Education in Nigeria

Dr James Azuka Olisa

Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

School Of Secondary Education (Technical)

Drjameszaukaolisa@gmail.com

Mr Frank Okoh

And

Mrs Felicia Osakue

Abstract

Research reports indicate that achievement of students in Automobile such as poor method of instructional technique and inadequate A need therefore arises for exploring more effective learning methodology in teaching and learning of automobile technology. It was therefore imperative to investigate the effectiveness of cooperative learning method in teaching and learning automobile technology which has not been ascertained. It was therefore imperative to investigate the students achievement in Automobile technology. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The instrument for data collection was a checklist and a questionnaire. The instrument was face-validated by 3 experts. Two of the experts were from the Department of Education Management, University of Port-Harcourt while the third from Measurement and Evaluation Department, University of Port-Harcourt. A reliability index of 0.88, using Ginbech Alpha formula was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis. Finding revealed among others that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the ATAT. There were significant differences between the mean achievement of the experimental ad control group in the Automobile Technology Achievement Test (ATAT). It was recommended that Automobile Technology teachers, school administrators should incorporate the use of simulation-based learning in College of Education (Technical) NCE programme to promote the acquisition of Automobile Technology psychomotor skills among others.

Introduction

Imparting adequate skills and self-reliance requires a good teaching method capable of facilitating effective learning. Research findings have shown that teaching and learning in the school system is predominantly teacher-centered and teacher directed (Boyle, 2003). The teacher centered activities may not be effective in teaching and learning Automobile Technology because the students ought to practice, demonstrate and show a certain degree of proficiency in the skills being demonstrated by the teacher. No educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Teaching is the process of guidance by which the learner is made to grasp ideas and facts and develop skills. It is the process of transmitting knowledge and skills (Nweke, 2007). More so teaching is the process of developing the cognitive, affective and psychomotor abilities of the learner through giving the learner knowledge of facts about subject matters, reinforcing or developing positive attitude in learner and also developing in the learner certain physical or manipulative skills (Edozie, 2006). It is a series of activities designed and performed to produce desirable change in students' behavior. According to Davis (2005), teaching takes place when information (or some skill) is communicated from teacher to pupils. If there is no communication, there is no teaching. If what is taught is not communicated, the attempt at teaching is unsuccessful. This shows that teaching presupposes learning.

Learning and teaching are like two sides of a coin. Okoh (2006) defined learning as a relatively lasting change in behavior that is induced directly by practice or relevant experience. This definition implies that for learning to take place there must be: A direct inducement, and this inducement is by direct experience. There must be a relatively permanent change in behavior.

This change in behavior could be cognitive, affective and psychomotor-related. When this happens, learning becomes holistic. According to Wikipedia (2017), learning is the process of acquiring new or modifying and reinforcing existing knowledge, behaviors, skills, values, or preferences which may lead to a potential change in synthesizing information, depth of the knowledge, attitude or behavior relative to the type and range of experience. Brown (2004) learning is also the acquisition of knowledge or skill gained through education. Rivgo (2005) asserts that learning may be made interesting by a blend of strategies. Blended learning is the combination

of multiple approaches to learning. Blended learning is facilitated by effective combination of different modes of instructional delivery, models of teaching and style of learning (Heinze, 2004). Learning method is the manner or form in which the teacher organizes the environment to facilitate student's assimilation. Pollock (2007) explained that, certain factors denote the learning method adopted by the teacher, they include, nature of the course (theory or practical) size of the class, time allotted and course content.

There are different types of teaching and learning method which includes the following:

Lecture method, Demonstration method, Dramatic method, Discovery or development method, Project Method, Socratic or Questioning method, Dalton plan or going at your own pace, comparative method, storytelling method (Iloh, 2008). Learning modes are divided into four broad categories namely: cooperative, competitive, cooperative-competitive and individualistic (Edozie2006). Learning mode could be seen as a catalyst in the educational system. In the context of this study cooperative and simulation learning method is implored.

Regarding cooperative learning style, students of different levels of ability work together in small group (5-10) to achieve a common purpose (Akinbolola, (2006). It involves the use of a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject (Slavin, 2003). Knowles and Kinsey (2005) explained that student in a group interacts with each other, share ideas and information and make decisions about their findings to the entire class. Holubeck (2007) presents the essential element of cooperative learning as positive inter-social skill and face to face interaction.

Olisa (2010) stated that cooperative learning method (CLM) could be used as an effective technique for enhancing student's achievement in technical course. Cooperative learning method is a simulation learning group-initiated mode that attempts to establish accountability within the group (Slavin, Maddeen & Stevens, 2008). Kovaliki (2005) discovered cooperative learning as the method of instruction, organized so that a group of students work together to reach a common goal. Technical college students' performance in various trades could be enhanced by using cooperative learning organization. Studies have shown that cooperative learning method has improved student's attitudes towards learning, self-esteem and intergroup relationship (Slavin 2007). CLM

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also enhances integrated process and product assessment mechanism needed for evaluation in psychomotor domain (Altherson, 2006). The teacher in this method blends the learning situations by grouping the student's and subjecting them to competitive testing while evaluating their psychomotor domain.

Edozie (2006) states that cooperative learning refers to students working together to achieve a common goal. It is learning that occurs when students work in small groups to help each other learn. It usually entails grouping students in small groups of 4 to 6. Cooperative learning may take different forms. Good cooperative learning in the classroom requires that time be spent on team-building skills, helping students become listeners, giving students practice on how to make contributions to group effort.

Researchers have found that cooperative learning can be an effective strategy for improving student's achievement, especially when group goals and individual accountability are instituted. Cooperative learning improves intrinsic motivation, encourages student's interdependence, and promotes deep understanding. It reduces social distance among students and improves self-worth and productivity. According to Slavin, (2007), Cooperative learning develops general mutual concern and interpersonal trust among students and increases students propensity for pro-social behaviour.

Research findings further show that compared with other methods, cooperative learning produces greater academic learning, better intergroup relations among different races, enhanced self-esteem, and improved relationships between mainstreamed academically handicapped students and normal-progress students. It promote group spirit (esprit de corps). According to Jarolimek (2006) cooperative learning is particularly useful in social studies. Cooperative learning is also referred to as collaborative learning. Vygotsky and Bandura's social learning theories provide the theoretical framework for cooperative learning. Ransdeel and Moberly (2003), opine that cooperative learning is a viable but under-used teaching-learning tool. They contend that educator can best utilize this method in their classrooms more effectively if they themselves were active participant in their teacher education training programme. Meng (2005), examines the application of cooperative learning method in the Chinese. He found that the nature of the Chinese

culture which is marked by collectivism enable this learning method to be more successful. Collectivism places emphasis on a more extended self which is understood in a wider context that is in relation to a physical and social environment which one seeks to harmonize (Meng, 2005). Meng (2005) outlines on experiment conducted by Tang (1996), in Hong Kong in which he tested to collaboration and their distribution of test and assignment.

Based on the finding Chinese student tended to be in cooperative learning groups which were at time spontaneous student Centre and based on group effort individual reward structure. This cultural phenomenon of collectivism is opposite to the western idea of individualism, Meng (2005) in concluding indicate that cooperative learning method is an effective motivating method and can be applied to many instructional fields.

Miller (2003) compares student's outcome following the use of problem based learning versus simulation teaching method for teaching in a theoretical graduate pharmacology course over a semester. She found that while the lecture delivery was a more effective way of teaching particular material, the final course average produced a normal distribution in both group of students' those exposed to problem-base learning and those exposed to simulation teaching method. The finding infer that there is virtually no difference with respects to students performance. Students and teachers will benefit more if both simulation and modern methods are fuse together in order to create a more effective, fun and interactive learning experience.

Technical colleges are institutions where students are trained to acquire relevant knowledge and skills in different occupations for employment in the world of work (National Board for Technical Education) (NBTE 2000). According to Federal Ministry of Education (2004), a technical college is a segment of technical and vocational education (TVE) designed to produce craftsmen at the secondary school level and master at the advanced craft. The goal of technical colleges as stated in the Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2004) are to, provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technician levels, provide the technical knowledge and impact the necessary skills to individual who shall be self-reliant economically.

Automobile Technology involves the application of scientific knowledge in the design, selection of materials, construction, operation and maintenance of automobile. Automobile Technology is one of the mechanical trades offered as motor vehicle mechanics work trade in Nigeria Technical colleges (Federal Republic of Nigeria) (FRN, 2004). The programme for motor vehicle mechanics trades in Nigeria technical college is designed to produce competent auto mechanics craftsmen in various automobile trades. Automobile trades involves repairs and maintenance of brake, transmission, engine, fuel, cooling and lubrication system on a motor vehicle. According to National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2001) auto-mechanics craftsman is expected to test, diagnose, service and completely repair any fault relating to the simulation automobile assembly main units and systems to the manufacturer's specification. This task calls for an instructional strategy that is capable of facilitating student's interest in learning. Gender issue has assumed prominence in technical and vocational education discourse. Some studies have shown that there is differential performance in activities as a result of gender. Ware and Lee (2007) found that number of enrolment in technical education courses was significantly fewer for female. In addition, Trusty (2008) examined the effects of background variables on choices of courses in colleges. He found that performance is positively affected by courses taken, which in turn, positively affect the choice of occupational field chosen later. It is possible gender can be a factor when considering learning strategies.

International Labour Organization (ILO) and United Nations Education and Scientific Cultural Organization (UNESCO 2002), stressed the need to seek for appropriate learning style and instructional technique that is student centered. The integration of cooperative learning style may assist the Automobile Technology student in the technical colleges to benefit from a shift from teacher centered to student centered for better acquisition of problem solving skill and thinking skill that can make room for lifelong learning.

Statement of the Problem

The technical colleges in the sixties had been a feed pipe to the industries for the supply of middle level manpower like craftsmen and technician owing to the fact that, the products of the technical college are well baked in skills related to the industrial work. Industries like Nigeria breweries

limited, Guinness Nigeria plc. textiles and manufacturing industries scramble and request from technical college administrators of their interest in their products on graduation. The reverse is the case now as the technical college products are now neither interested in possessing the basic skills needed by the industries nor responsible skills to build upon for industrial use, the industries thereby no longer request from the school nor employ when student come to seek for employment but rather prefers to develop their in-house staff by owing training schools.

The effectiveness of cooperative learning method on the learning of Automobile Technology courses is yet to be ascertained the question then is "would cooperative learning method increase performance of students in Automobile Technology" this research project would investigate the performance of technical education students (automobile) in technical colleges in Anambra State when they taught with the cooperative learning method in order to find out whether such teaching and learning method could be exploited. It is therefore imperative to investigate the effectiveness of Cooperative learning method on students achievement in Automobile Technology.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to determine the effectiveness of cooperative learning method on student achievement in Automobile Technology. Specifically, the study;

1. Determined the significant difference that exist in the use of cooperative learning method (CLM) and simulation teaching method in teaching and learning of Automobile Technology.
2. Find out what group of students performed better in Automobile Technology achievement test (ATAT).
3. Find out what group of students performed better in the Automobile Technology education retention test (ATRT).

Research Question

The following research questions were answered in the study

1. What is the significant difference that exist in the use of cooperative learning method and simulation teaching method in teaching and learning Automobile Technology in technical colleges in Anambra State?
2. What group of students performed better in Automobile Technology Achievement Test (ATAT)?
3. What group of students performed better in the Automobile Technology retention Test (ATRT)?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. It provides the opinion of the respondents on the effects of school structures and environment on performance of secondary School students in Oshimili South Local Government Area. Nwogu (2006) defines descriptive survey design as that study which aims at collecting data and describes in a systematic way, the features of a given population. However, this design is considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to identify the characteristics of the population objectively. The population for this study consisted of all the teachers and students in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Owing to the huge population size, Taro Yamane sampling techniques was used to determine the exact number of respondents to be quizzed, which was approximately 374. Therefore, the sample size for the study was 374 subjects (72 teachers and 302 students). Simple random sampling techniques was used for sampling

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. Primary sources of data were original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. In collecting primary data for the work, responses were elicited from the teachers and students of secondary schools. These are data mainly sourced from already made materials of other authors and researchers. They are available in relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers and internet. The instrument for data collection was a checklist and a questionnaire. The questionnaire had two sections, A and B. Section A contained

information on personal data of the respondents, while section B, contained items on influence of Educational Facilities on Academic Achievements. The instrument was face-validated by 3 experts. Two of the experts were from the Department of Education Management, University of Port-Harcourt while the third from Measurement and Evaluation Department, University of Port-Harcourt. These experts were given the initial copies of the questionnaire as well as the purpose, research questions and hypotheses to critically examine the adequacy of the items and the weighing of the responses. These comments, suggestions and criticisms made independently by the experts helped the researcher to modify and produce the final draft of the instrument.

The ATAT was trial-tested on twenty six (26) Automobile Technology Education students in Government Technical College Iselle-uku, Delta State and the results were used to determine the reliability of the ATAT. A reliability index of 0.88, using Ginbech Alpha formula was obtained. The value indicated that the ATAT was reliable and therefore adequate for the study. Prior to the middle of third term two intact Automobile Technology education classes at Government Technical College Onitsha, Precisely NTC (3) were randomly assigned to treatment condition. One class was randomly chosen and taught Automobile Technology course using simulation teaching method and acted as the control group and the other class was taught the same subject using the cooperative learning method and acted as the experimental group. The two groups were taught for three weeks. A pre-test on Automobile Technology was administered to both groups before the treatment. The Automobile Technology course as taught within 60 minutes in one week. The same researcher taught both groups with the help of the students head teacher. In the control group, the researcher instructed student to learn the automobile Technology contents using simulation teaching method.

In the treatment group, the researcher guided students to learn the Automobile Technology contents using cooperative learning method. In this group the researcher supplied the following three steps:

1. The researcher organized the learning materials and identified the objectives of the subject matter.
2. Student help each other to learn their learning materials and

3. The researcher assessed students' understanding through their presentation in front of the whole class.

This process was repeated (3) times, once for each unit of work.

Throughout the experiment both groups could not meet at the same time as they were taught by the researcher. The treatment group was taught on Fridays from 11am-12pm while the control group was taught on the same Friday 1pm-2pm with the permission of the head of department. Both groups covered the same amount of time precisely for 6 weeks. After the treatment, both groups took post-test (ATAT) to measure students' achievement. Seven days after, a retention test was administered to both groups. Scores thus obtained provided the required data for analysis. To determine the effectiveness of ATAT on the groups, the mean scores and standard deviation of the experimental and control groups were compared on the measures.

Results

Research Question 1: What significant difference exist in the use of simulation and cooperative learning method on NCE students academic achievement in Automobile Technology?

Table 1: Mean score and standard deviation for experimental and control group and ATAT.

Groups	Ns	\bar{x}	
Experimental (SM)	26	40.69	3.48
Control (CTM)	26	29.57	4.08

Table 1 shows the mean achievement score and standard deviation of the experimental and control group. The experimental group has a mean score of 40.69 and a standard deviation of 3.48; while the mean score and standard deviation for the control group 29.57 and 4.08 respectively. These values indicate that the difference in scores was in favour of the experimental group which recorded higher mean score. The implication is that SM proved more effective than the CLM techniques as an instructional technique for teaching and learning Automobile Technology.

Research Question 2: What group of students performed better in the Automobile Technology Achievement Test (ATAT)?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation for experimental and control groups in Automobile Technology Achievement Test (ATAT)

S/N	Group	Year of Study	NS	$\bar{x}a$	SDa	NS	$\bar{x}b$	SDb
1	Experimental (SM)	NCE 3A	13	43.76	4.73	13	45.15	3.51
		NCE 3B	13	40.61	3.4	13	45.76	4.14
2	Control (CTM)	NCE 3A	13	30.53	4.41	13	29.30	6.41
		NCE 3B	13	29.25	3.40	13	30.23	6.0

Table 2 show the mean achievement score and standard deviation of the experimental and control groups by year of study with different sub-groups. The experimental group has high mean achievement score in both the pre-test and post-test. This indicates that experimental group in NCE 3 group A and B performed better than the control group in NCE 3A and B in the Automobile Technology Achievement Tests. The implication again is that CLM group proved more effective than the CTM technique as an instructional technique for teaching and learning Automobile Technology courses.

Research Question 3: What group of students performed better in the Automobile Technology Retention Test (ATRT)?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation for experimental and control groups in Automobile Technology Retention Test (ATRT)

S/N	Group	Post – Test			Retention Test		
		NS	$\bar{x}b$	SD	NS	$\bar{x}c$	SD
1	Experimental (SM)	26	42.1	2.37	26	49.65	8.12
2	Control (CTM)	26	29.76	6.23	26	30.36	3.76

Table 3 shows the mean score and standard deviation of the experimental and control group in the retention test. The experimental group has higher achievement score in both the post-test and retention test. This indicates that experimental group performed better than the control group in the Automobile Technology Retention Test. The implication is that SM proved more effective than the CTM technique as an instructional technique for teaching and learning Automobile Technology.

Discussion

The research question one for the study could be answered from table 1. The experimental group had a mean score of 40.69 and standard deviation of 3.48, while the mean score and standard deviation for the control group were 29.57 and 4.03 respectively. These values indicated that the experimental group performed better than the control group at the ATAT. There were significant differences between the mean achievement of the experimental and control group in the Automobile Technology Achievement Test (ATAT). These differences can be attributed to the simulation teaching method which motivates students understanding of Automobile Technology (Adebayo, 2024). Evidence from this study, indicated that the SCM had a significant effect on students achievement in Automobile Technology. Teachers should therefore explore and use SCM to boost learning outcomes.

Research question two is about the learning method that produced better result by year of study from table 2, the post treatment mean for the NC 3 group A and B students were 45.15 and 43.16 respectively for the experimental group. These values are higher than that of the NCE 3A and B students in the control group. This indicates that the group A and B of NCE 3 students in the experimental group performed better than their control group counterpart. Once more, results indicates that the experimental group for the NCE 3 was better than the control group for the NCE 3 students.

Regarding research question three, the experimental group has high achievement score in both the post-test and retention-test. This indicates once more that the experimental group performed better than the control group in Automobile Technology Retention Test (ATRTR). This

findings is in consistent with that of Okeke (2023) who found that SCM enhances students achievement in science, technology and mathematics (STM).

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that simulation-based learning enhances students' achievements. The teachers of Automobile Technology should as much as possible promote simulation-based learning to boost students performance in Automobile Technology. The poor performance of students in Automobile Technology could be linked in part to the use of unsuitable and inappropriate methods of instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the subsequent discussion and their implication, the following recommendations were made.

1. Automobile Technology teachers, school administrators should incorporate the use of simulation-based learning in College of Education (Technical) NCE programme to promote the acquisition of Automobile Technology psychomotor skills.
2. In-service training, conferences and workshops should be organized by relevant stakeholders for Automobile Technology teachers on effective use of simulation-based learning to improve their knowledge and skills.
3. In-lime with the above recommendations, there is also an urgent need for curriculum developers and planners to review prevailing instructional strategies prevalent in colleges of education which has become obsolete and then re-formulate policies and programmes that will encourage the use of simulation-based learning.

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